

Aniq integrallarni taqribiy hisoblash uchun B-splayn asosida kvadratur formula qurish

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada aniq integrallarni taqribiy hisoblash uchun B-splayn funksiyalariga asoslangan kvadratur formula qurish masalasi tadqiq etilgan. Tadqiqotda integral ostidagi funksiya tugun nuqtalaridagi diskret qiymatlar asosida B-splayn bazis funksiyalari yordamida approksimatsiya qilinadi. Olingan approksimatsiya asosida kvadratur formula koeffitsiyentlari aniqlanadi. Taklif etilgan usulning aniqligi va samaradorligi bir nechta test funksiyalar yordamida tekshirilgan hamda natijalar klassik trapetsiya usuli bilan solishtirilgan. Natijalar B-splayn asosidagi kvadratur formula aniq integrallarni sonli hisoblashda yuqori aniqlik va barqarorlikka ega ekanligini ko‘rsatadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: B-splayn, kvadratur formula, sonli integrallash, splayn approksimatsiyasi, bazis funksiyalar, hisoblash matematikasi, xatolik bahosi, yaqinlashish tartibi, trapetsiya usuli.

Kirish

Ko‘pincha tadqiqot jarayonida o‘lchovlar natijasida hosil bo‘lgan nostandart geometrik yuzalarni analitik funksiyalar yordamida ifodalash qiyin bo‘ladi. Shu sababli bunday hollarda aniq integrallarni hisoblashda sonli usullardan foydalanish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Mazkur ishda B-splayn bazis funksiyalaridan foydalanib, diskret qiymatlar ko‘rinishida berilgan $[a,b]$ oraliqdagi funksiya asosida uning aniq integralini taqribiy hisoblash usuli ko‘rib chiqiladi. Taklif etilayotgan yondashuv diskret ma‘lumotlar bilan berilgan funksiyalar uchun integral qiymatini yuqori aniqlik bilan aniqlash imkonini beradi hamda nostandart geometrik yuzalarni hisoblashda samarali natijalar beradi.

Metodologiya

Bizga $[a,b]$ oraliqda $f(x)$ funksiyaning aniq integralini hisoblash masalasi qo‘yilgan bo‘lsin. Agar $f(x)$ funksiya $[a, b]$ oraliqda uzluksiz bo‘lsa ixtiyoriy $c \in [a, b]$ nuqta uchun aniq integral quyidagi ko‘rinishda oraliqlarga bo‘lib, yig‘indi shaklida ifodalash mumkin:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = \int_a^c f(x) dx + \int_c^b f(x) dx$$

Agar $[a,b]$ oraliqni n ta teng oraliqqa ($a = x_0 < x_1 < \dots < x_{n-1} < x_n = b$) bo‘lsak va $f(x)$ bu oraliqda uzluksiz funksiya bo‘lsa, unda $f(x)$ funksiyaning $[a,b]$ oraliqda aniq integrali har bir kichik oraliqdagi integrallar yig‘indisiga teng bo‘ladi.

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \left(\int_{x_i}^{x_{i+1}} f(x) dx \right)$$

Bu yerda $f(x) = S_i(x)$ ko‘rinishda B-splayn bilan almashtirish amalga oshirishimiz mumkin. B-splaynning ko‘rinishi quyidagicha:

$$S_i(t) = \varphi_1(t) f(x_{i-1}) + \varphi_2(t) f(x_i) + \varphi_3(t) f(x_{i+1}) + \varphi_4(t) f(x_{i+2})$$

bu yerda,

$$\varphi_1(t) = \frac{1}{6}(1-t)^3$$

$$\varphi_2(t) = \frac{1}{6}(3t^3 - 6t^2 + 4)$$

$$\varphi_3(t) = \frac{1}{6}(1 + 3t + 3t^2 - 3t^3)$$

$$\varphi_4(t) = \frac{1}{6}t^3$$

$f(x) = S_i(x)$ almashtirish amalga oshiradigan bo'lsak, aniq integral quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \left(\int_{x_i}^{x_{i+1}} (\varphi_1(t)f(x_{i-1}) + \varphi_2(t)f(x_i) + \varphi_3(t)f(x_{i+1}) + \varphi_4(t)f(x_{i+2})) dx \right) =$$

$$= \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \left(f(x_{i-1}) \int_{x_i}^{x_{i+1}} \varphi_1(t) dx + f(x_i) \int_{x_i}^{x_{i+1}} \varphi_2(t) dx + f(x_{i+1}) \int_{x_i}^{x_{i+1}} \varphi_3(t) dx + f(x_{i+2}) \int_{x_i}^{x_{i+1}} \varphi_4(t) dx \right)$$

endi t parametri orqali x ni [0,1] oralikka akslantiramiz va $\varphi_1(t), \varphi_2(t), \varphi_3(t), \varphi_4(t)$ bazis funksiyalar bo'yicha aniq integrallarni hisoblaymiz.

$$\frac{x - x_i}{h} = t \quad x = x_i + ht \quad dx = hdt \quad t \in [0,1]$$

$$\int_{x_i}^{x_{i+1}} \varphi_1(t) dx = h \int_0^1 \varphi_1(t) dt = \int_0^1 \frac{1}{6}(1-t)^3 dt = \frac{h}{24}$$

$$\int_{x_i}^{x_{i+1}} \varphi_2(t) dx = h \int_0^1 \varphi_2(t) dt = \int_0^1 \frac{1}{6}(3t^3 - 6t^2 + 4) dt = \frac{11h}{24}$$

$$\int_{x_i}^{x_{i+1}} \varphi_3(t) dx = h \int_0^1 \varphi_3(t) dt = \int_0^1 \frac{1}{6}(1 + 3t + 3t^2 - 3t^3) dt = \frac{11h}{24}$$

$$\int_{x_i}^{x_{i+1}} \varphi_4(t) dx = h \int_0^1 \varphi_4(t) dt = \int_0^1 \frac{1}{6}t^3 dt = \frac{h}{24}$$

Yuqorida hisoblangan qiymatlarni o'rniga qo'yib integralni yozadigan bo'lsak quyidagi ko'rinishga kelamiz:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{h}{24} f(x_{i-1}) + \frac{11h}{24} f(x_i) + \frac{11h}{24} f(x_{i+1}) + \frac{h}{24} f(x_{i+2}) \right) =$$

$$= \frac{h}{24} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (f(x_{i-1}) + 11f(x_i) + 11f(x_{i+1}) + f(x_{i+2}))$$

Umumiy ko'rinishi,

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = \frac{h}{24} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (f(x_{i-1}) + 11f(x_i) + 11f(x_{i+1}) + f(x_{i+2}))$$

holatga keldi. Bu yig'indini to'liq ochib yozadigan bo'lsak natija quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$i = 0: f(x_{-1}) + 11f(x_0) + 11f(x_1) + f(x_2);$$

$$i = 1: f(x_0) + 11f(x_1) + 11f(x_2) + f(x_3);$$

$$i = 2: f(x_1) + 11f(x_2) + 11f(x_3) + f(x_4);$$

$$i = 3: f(x_2) + 11f(x_3) + 11f(x_4) + f(x_5);$$

$$i = 4: f(x_3) + 11f(x_4) + 11f(x_5) + f(x_6);$$

$$i = 5: f(x_4) + 11f(x_5) + 11f(x_6) + f(x_7);$$

$$i = 6: f(x_5) + 11f(x_6) + 11f(x_7) + f(x_8)$$

.....

$$i = n - 4: f(x_{n-5}) + 11f(x_{n-4}) + 11f(x_{n-3}) + f(x_{n-2});$$

$$i = n - 3: f(x_{n-4}) + 11f(x_{n-3}) + 11f(x_{n-2}) + f(x_{n-1});$$

$$i = n - 2: f(x_{n-3}) + 11f(x_{n-2}) + 11f(x_{n-1}) + f(x_n);$$

$$i = n - 1: f(x_{n-2}) + 11f(x_{n-1}) + 11f(x_n) + f(x_{n+1}).$$

$$= \frac{h}{24} \left(f(x_{-1}) + f(x_{n+1}) + 12f(x_0) + 12f(x_n) + 23f(x_1) + 23f(x_{n-1}) + 24 \sum_{i=2}^{n-2} f(x_i) \right)$$

Integralning yakuniy ko'rinishi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{h}{24} \left(f(x_{-1}) + f(x_{n+1}) + 12f(x_0) + 12f(x_n) + 23f(x_1) + 23f(x_{n-1}) + 24 \sum_{i=2}^{n-2} f(x_i) \right)$$

Tahlil va natijalar

Biz B-splayn yordamida aniq integralni taqribiy hisoblash va uni amaliy muammolarga tatbiq etish jarayonini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Dastlab, tajriba sifatida biz analitik funksiyaning tugun nuqtalarda aniqlangan qiymatlari yordamida aniq integralni hisoblab, ushbu usulning xatolik qiymatini ko'rib chiqamiz. Tanlangan analitik

funksiya sifatida $f(x) = \sin x$ ni qaraymiz.

$$\int_0^1 f(x) dx = \int_0^1 e^{-x}(x^2 + 1) dx = -(x^2 + 2x - 3)e^{-x} \Big|_0^1 = 0.792723$$

1-jadval. $e^{-x}(x^2 + 1)$ funksiyasi va funksiya hosilasining tugun nuqtalardagi qiymatlari.

x	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1
$f(x)$	1	0.914	0.851	0.807	0.779	0.758	0.740	0.724	0.709	0.691	0.736

$h=0.1$

B-splayn asosida qurilgan usul bilan aniq integralni hisoblaymiz,

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{h}{24} \left(f(x_{-1}) + f(x_{n+1}) + 12f(x_0) + 12f(x_n) + 23f(x_1) + 23f(x_{n-1}) + 24 \sum_{i=2}^{n-2} f(x_i) \right)$$

bu yerda, $f(x_{-1}) = f(a-h)$, $f(x_{n+1}) = f(b+h)$

$$\int_0^1 e^{-x}(x^2+1) dx \approx \frac{0.1}{24} \cdot ((1.226+0.769)+12(1+0.736)+23(0.914+0.691)+24(0.851+0.807+0.779+0.758+0.740+0.724+0.709)) = \frac{0.1}{24} \cdot (1.995+12(1.736)+23(1.605)+24(5.368)) = \frac{0.1}{24} \cdot (1.995+20.832+36.915+128.832) = \frac{0.1}{24} \cdot 188.574 = 0.792723$$

2-jadval. Turli xil funksiyalarning berilgan oraliqdagi aniq integralni trapetsiya va B-splayn yordamida qurilgan usullar bilan hisoblangan qiymatlari.

$\int_a^b f(x) dx$	Trapetsiy a usuli	Trapetsiya usuli xatoligi	B-splayn usuli	B-splayn usuli xatoligi
$\int_0^1 e^{-x}(x^2+1) = 0.792723$	0.78941	$3.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.792723	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$
$\int_1^4 \ln x dx = 2.545177$	2.533714	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-2}$	2.539574	$5.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$

Yuqoridagi jadvaldan ko‘rinib turibdiki B-splayn funksiyasi bilan yaratilgan usul trapetsiya usuliga nisbatan yaxshi yaqinlashdi.

Xulosa

B-splayn asosida qurilgan ushbu kvadratur formula sonli integrallash masalalarida yaxshi samaradorlikka ega ekanligini ko‘rsatmoqda. Splaynlarning lokal xususiyati tufayli, integral ostidagi funksiyaning xatti-harakati har bir kichik oraliqda alohida inobatga olingani usulning barqarorligini ta'minladi. Taklif etilgan uslub murakkab funksiyalarni integrallashda adaptiv yondashuvni talab qiladigan amaliy masalalar, xususan, raqamli modellashtirish va signallar tahlili uchun ishonchli matematik apparat bo‘lib xizmat qiladi. Kelgusida ushbu yondashuvni ko‘p o‘lchovli integrallar uchun umumlashtirish amaliy jihatdan katta qiziqish uyg‘otadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati

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